

Secondary English Students' Attitudes toward Learning English: A case study in Cambodia

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Abstract—

A group of students from a well-known private school in Banteay Meanchey Province, Cambodia, were randomly selected as a sample for this research study. Most of these students' parents work to the best of their lives for their children's education, mainly English education, whether they are employees of Thai businesspeople or business owners in Thailand. Despite frequently communicating in Thai for business purposes, those parents always encourage their children to learn English. Accordingly, educational stakeholders around Cambodia and the globe can benefit from this study by being informed of the student's reflections in general. The study aimed to investigate the attitudes of secondary-level students studying English and the comparison of the attitudes of males and females towards learning English. Mythologically, this study employed a quantitative method and an Independent sample test to compare the students' genders using SPSS 22. The findings indicate that the secondary students highly valued the 5th item on the list provided in the questionnaire, which showed that they positively encouraged all Cambodian students to consider English as the must language to learn. That is why obtaining academic credentials is necessary for those to continue their education after high school, which is likely one of their primary goals. Next, they preferred English to take advantage of the technological advances of the present day. After that, they felt motivated to pursue opportunities to study abroad and acquire English for professional purposes. Remarkably, the survey revealed high confidence that they regarded English as the most essential and desirable subject among all others and could easily use it for all types of communication. Future research should focus on using a mixed method on two or more schools in the province, as the author of this study used a quantitative method on only one school.

Keywords: English, abroad, attitudes, Secondary, private, Cambodia, confidence

INTRODUCTION

Banteay Meanchey, situated in the northwestern region of Cambodia, is geographically next to Thailand, Oddar Meanchey, Siem Reap, and Battambang provinces. The distance between Banteay Meanchey and Phnom Penh, the capital city of Cambodia, is about 359 kilometers, accessible through national Route 5. The school studied was one of the well-known schools in Poipet Town, Banteaymeanchey Province, Cambodia. Among more than 3000 students, 909 are in the primary and secondary levels of the English program. Trading between Cambodia and Thailand is so popular that most understudied students' parents commute for business. They want to produce educated children; however, the fruitful information related to the students' attitudes, which can help those parents seek ways to support their children in better English, secretly stays inside this research study, called Secondary English Students' Attitudes toward Learning English: A Case Study in Cambodia. So English is crucial to those students, which is the core interest of their parents' concern. According to previous studies, Thailand has attracted around 6 million unskilled immigrant laborers and their accompanying family members from neighboring countries. Two hundred thousand individuals from southern Thailand relocated to Malaysia for employment opportunities (Krainara & Routray, 2015). The primary demographic of the Cambodian population residing in Thailand, specifically in Banteay Meanchey province, consists of migrant workers. The key informants concluded

through the interview that migrant workers residing in rural migrant settlements such as Mouy Village and Pii Village. These interviews shed light on the substantial influence of migration decisions on the population, as mentioned earlier (Chaichanavichakit, 2022).

For economic reconstruction and assimilation, English is a crucial international language in Cambodia, Vietnam, and Japan. Despite inadequate instruction, English remains indispensable in the nation's science, information, technology, and education. Non-native English speakers are becoming more fluent in the language, especially in Asian, African, and Pacific countries where it is an official language. According to a 1999 National Institute of Languages in Japan survey, English is the most suitable language for international communication, and many students have attained proficiency (Honna, 2005). English proficiency is crucial for Malaysia's development goals, but teachers' unrealistic views on teaching oral communication skills in English classrooms can lead to poor speaking performance (Aziz & Kashinathan, 2021). For instance, teachers at Accra Senior High School conducted a case study to investigate the attitudes and motivation of students toward English language learning. The study, which involved 100 students and five teachers, revealed that students are motivated to learn English for their studies, to communicate with English speakers, and to secure a well-paying job (Anokye, 2022). Globalization, economic expansion, and cultural influences have made English a vital language for science, business, and international communication. Since Cambodia joined ASEAN in 1999, English has become the preferred foreign language for trade and education (Kruy, September 2023).

English is a globally significant language, utilized extensively in education and the workplace in Thailand, with job postings emphasizing the need for proficient English speakers (Imsa-Ard, 2020). Vietnamese widely speak English due to economic integration, but the quality of English instruction still needs improvement, causing many students to struggle for survival (Vu & Peters, 2021). English is a vital international language in science, information, technology, and education. Since 1989, English as a Foreign Language (EFL) classrooms have been implemented in Cambodia, ensuring students are engaged in language learning (Chhoeut & Taewattana, 2022). Based on the study by Kruy (August 2023), Cambodian teachers need help with English reading motivation, as only some teachers can speak English effectively. Thus, English using English as a Foreign Language in classrooms is essential in Cambodia. Mahu (2012) similarly says that English is the most widely spoken language worldwide; 1 in 5 individuals can comprehend it. Estimatedly, there are 380 million native speakers, 300 million people who speak English as a second language, and 100 million people who speak English as a foreign language.

Attitudes are summaries of assessments; they are not always objective, belief-based conclusions. Analysis and "hot" emotive responses are both included in the evaluation. Attitudes are widespread and typically long-lasting assessments of other people, things, or ideas. Petty, Briol, and DeMarree (2007) define *attitudes* as people's overall summary assessments that can be their positivity or negativity (Briñol, 2019). Attitudes include individuals' overall and permanent assessments of others, things, or concepts. In other terms, *attitudes* might be defined as individuals' overall assessments, characterized by their positive or negative orientation (Petty et al., 2007 in Briñol, 2019). Attitude strength pertains specifically to the variability in the activation of attitudes. The attitude strength of a variable is influenced by its social distribution. Variables with a more prominent social distribution are likelier to possess elevated levels of attitude strength.

The study examines the attitudes of secondary English students at a highly esteemed private institution, focusing on gender differences and the need for future mixed-method research across multiple institutions in the province.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

This study aims to answer the following questions:

1. To what extent do Cambodian secondary private students' attitudes toward learning English?
2. Is there any difference in the attitudes between males and females of the secondary students toward learning English?

LITERATURE REVIEW

People in the world use English as a foreign language in Cambodia, primarily in international commerce and education. The UNTAC period in Cambodia and its subsequent admittance into ASEAN have led to a notable growth in the use of the English language. Cambodia is now transitioning from poverty, which has prompted the revision of the elementary school curriculum to prioritize the development of English language ability (Kruy,

September 2023). Only a few people in Cambodia speak English well despite its high reputation. Instructing young kids who are learning English presents challenges for elementary school teachers. Educational professionals, trainers, and others in education must encourage a love of reading, as shown by several studies. Very few studies have examined reading motivation in connection to Cambodia (Kruy, August 2023). English had dramatically influenced Cambodia since the 1990s when English-speaking international institutions like the UN and ASEAN started offering more fabulous job and educational prospects. Because of this, Cambodians are now more competitive in local and regional employment markets, especially in the quickly expanding tourist sector. English-speaking Cambodians who joined the World Trade Organization benefit from increasing work prospects among ASEAN neighbors owing to their language skills. (Igawa, 2008, cited in Kruy, August 2023).

Additionally, acquiring English facilitates communication and integration with the local community, even from an English-speaking country (Mahu, 2012). Workplace tensions may rise when workers struggle to communicate with one another because of their insufficient understanding of the English language. In today's globalized corporate world, reading, writing, communicating, and listening fluently in English is essential for success (Adawiyah, 2021). Moreover, another previous study also shares the advantages of learning English. For instance, English is the language most spoken in the world now. That is because it is a specialized language used in the classroom. Thanks to it, we have access to a wide variety of written resources, both offline and online. It is excellent for taking on the road. English provides learners with an essential experience of seeking an international career and understanding Hollywood's language (Ilyosovna, 2020).

English language education benefits students by fostering intercultural competence, allowing them to adapt to diverse living, thinking, and communication patterns, and comprehending their and others' identities within a multicultural context. This knowledge provides valuable insight into one's and others' histories (Haukås et al., 2022). However, learners' attitudes always go together with learning English. The Psychology of Attitudes by Haddock and Maio defines attitudes as psychological tendencies expressed by liking or disliking a particular entity. As defined by Fazio (2007) and Bohner & Dickel (2011), Briol's framework focuses on associating an entity with a concise evaluation stored in the recipient's memory. The context influences individuals' attitudes toward the object (cited in Briñol, 2019).

As evaluative judgments, attitudes can vary along two dimensions: valence (positive or negative) and intensity (strong or weak). Positive attitudes, such as those toward the Welsh rugby team, may be positive, whereas negative attitudes, such as those toward liver, may be harmful. Strong attitudes, such as those regarding the Euro, can be weaker than those regarding the same subject (Haddock & Maio, 2008). The concept of attitude strength pertains to the durability and impact of an attitude, whereby strong attitudes exhibit greater longevity and exhibit heightened resistance to alteration. A phenomenon's intensity might decrease prior to confrontation, so making an influence on it (Briñol, 2019). Learning a foreign language is a second language acquisition influenced by learning style, motivation, and attitude. A positive mindset is crucial for success, as negative attitudes can cause anxiety, poor cognitive performance, and low motivation, impacting the learner's drive and mental ability (Mat & Yunus, 2014). We see the world through our attitudes; people who score highly on needs assessments have more positive attitudes and are less likely to decline an offer of assistance when asked in surveys (Briñol, 2019).

Attitudes are evaluations of an attitude object, and one of the most influential models is the multicomponent model. Attitudes synthesize an object's affective, cognitive, and behavioral evaluations. Researchers have investigated how these components contribute to the formation and expression of attitudes, considering how like-dislike evaluations can impact the overall evaluation of an attitude object (Haddock & Maio, 2008). According to Saville (2006), as cited in Anokye (2022), motivation and attitude are crucial for language learners' success. Drive and effort put into language learning phases determine the success rate. Oroujlou and Vahedi (2011) in Anokye (2022) discovered that motivation and attitude significantly improve students' language proficiency and efficiency. Therefore, a positive attitude and motivation are necessary for attaining the desired linguistic results. According to Eagly and Chaiken (1993), an attitude is a psychological tendency expressed by a favorable or unfavorable evaluation of a particular entity. This study's operational definition of attitude is students' views, understandings, beliefs, and experiences with learning English as a foreign language. (Al Noursi, 2013).

Kifayatullah et al. (2023) discovered that, regardless of gender, agriculture students have positive attitudes toward the English language and its four skills. However, female students exhibited somewhat more favorable attitudes toward English. Similarly, Ahmed (2015) pointed out a study that surveyed 238 Malaysian undergraduate EFL students to understand their attitudes towards English learning. Results showed a positive attitude, but students often had negative feelings or fear about classroom instructions. The study also revealed that students' attitudes

varied across different fields, suggesting that a single curriculum or teaching methodology needs to be revised. Alkaff (2013) pointed out that the study explores the attitudes and perceptions of 47 female Foundation Year students at King Abdulaziz University in Jeddah, Saudi Arabia, who must learn English. This study aims to comprehend their perspectives on the significance of English, its difficulty, and areas for improvement. Despite obstacles such as time constraints and limited practice opportunities, the results reveal that most students have a positive outlook on English learning.

Focusing on 190 eighth-grade students from a private primary school in Adana, this study investigates the relationship between English language attitudes and its use in Turkey. Students exposed to English more frequently have a moderately positive attitude toward the language, with female students exhibiting higher rates (Karahana, 2007). The article investigates Pakistani students' motivational orientations and attitudes toward learning English as a second language. The study found that participants had positive attitudes toward learning English and a helpful orientation. Urdu and English are highly esteemed, with Urdu serving as a symbol of national unity. Pakistani students are additively bilingual and favor English as their instructional medium for instrumental purposes (Khalid, 2016). The study focused on the behavioral, cognitive, and emotional attitudes of secondary school students in Libya towards English learning. The results revealed negative attitudes toward learning English, with significant gender, field, and year of study differences (Abidin et al., 2012).

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The study's researchers employed a technique known as "quantitative." A well-known private school with over 3,000 students, 909 enrolled in primary and secondary English courses, provided the sample group of fifty-six students. There were 300 people in the Secondary level. According to Loeb et al. (2017), which Krueger (August 2023) cites, descriptive research is helpful in the era of big data because it helps organize data into meaningful dimensions that researchers can utilize to identify trends and guide decision-making. It helps determine how all the different information about the education system fits together. The authors of this study used numbers to do their work. There are different kinds of quantitative designs. To collect data for the study, researchers employed a survey. Queirós (2017) also said that the goal of quantitative research is to be objective and that it is helpful to draw conclusions from population samples and measure different variables in numbers. Quantitative research uses formal tools and structured steps to gather data. The data are collected methodically and objectively. Researchers employed statistics and software such as Stata, R, or SPSS to examine data.

Data Collection

The authors used a survey consisting of 14 items to evaluate the opinions of a sample of fifty-six English private secondary students enrolled at a renowned private school in Poipet Town, Bantéay Méanchey Province, Cambodia. To efficiently explore the students' attitudes, the authors divided all items in the questionnaire into two main groups. The first group (9 items: 5, 12, 11, 10, 13, 1, 3, 9, and 2) checked the reasons that made students put effort into learning English. The second group (5 items: 4, 14, 7, 8, 6) aimed to explore whether students' attitudes were positive or negative. Horwitz et al. (1986) designed the questionnaire that Imron and Hantari (2019) used for their study. The study employed quantitative research methods, namely questionnaires, to collect data and examine the research issues. The dataset was analyzed with SPSS version 22 to identify significant fluctuations. Researchers evaluated the findings using frequency and percentages, descriptive statistics applied to the Likert scale, and correlation analysis, including the correlation coefficient and P-value. Rensis Likert created the Likert scale in 1932 to assess attitudes. It entails presenting a series of statements ranging from one to five, representing varying degrees of agreement or disagreement, with one representing strong disagreement and five representing strong agreement. According to the findings of the study conducted by Pimentel and Pimentel (2019), a five-point Likert scale is effective for measuring the variables under investigation.

Data Analysis

The authors of this paper adopted and modified a questionnaire from Kifaatullah et al. (2023). Before beginning data collection, the author thoroughly examined the questionnaire's items. A sample of fifty-six students revealed their attitudes through a 14-item survey. The authors analyzed quantitative data using SPSS 22 to determine the extent of their attitudes toward English language learning. The research centered on attitude dimensions and aimed to calculate each item's Mean and standard deviation.

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

English secondary students' demographic information

Table 1. Gender

Demographic	Value	N	Frequency %
Gender	Male	31	55.40%
	Female	25	44.60%
Total		56	100%

Table 2 shows that the total number of participants is 56. There are 31 (55.40%) male students and 25 (44.60%) female students. The number of female students is 10.80% less than the number of male students.

Table 1. Age

Demographic	Value	N	Frequency %
Age	below 15	21	37.50%
	15 - 16	32	57.10%
	17 - 18	3	5.40%
Total		56	100%

Table 2 shows that approximately 57.10% of all students are in the 15–16 age range. Then, three pupils, or roughly 5.40%, are in the 17–18 age range. Twenty-one students, or 37.50%, are surprisingly younger than 15. So, most English-language learners in secondary schools are between 15 and 16.

Table 3. Result of Primary students' attitudes toward learning English

No.	Items	N	M	SD	Min	Max
5	I think all students in Cambodia should learn English.	56	4.52	0.66	3.00	5.00
12	I want to learn English to help me in my University Education.	56	4.46	0.66	3.00	5.00
11	I want to learn English to get maximum advantage of the modern technologies and internet.	56	4.39	0.65	3.00	5.00
10	I want to learn English to get a good job.	56	4.30	0.69	3.00	5.00
13	I want to learn English to study abroad.	56	4.27	0.70	3.00	5.00
1	I feel excited when I learn English.	56	4.13	0.51	3.00	5.00
3	English is one of my favorite subjects.	56	4.02	0.80	2.00	5.00
9	I learn English because it can help me understand other academic subjects.	56	4.02	0.94	1.00	5.00
2	I practice English when I find an opportunity to do so.	56	3.79	0.62	3.00	5.00
Total of 9 items (5, 12, 11, 10, 13, 1, 3, 9, 2)		56	4.21	0.69	2.67	5.00
4	I think English is the most difficult language to learn.	56	2.77	1.01	1.00	5.00
14	Truly speaking, I want to learn English just to pass the exams"	56	2.3	1.03	1.00	5.00
7	I feel embarrassed and uneasy when studying English.	56	1.95	0.96	1.00	5.00
8	I don't consider learning English important.	56	1.84	0.91	1.00	5.00
6	I dislike English subject the most.	56	1.57	0.89	1.00	5.00
Total of 5 Items (4, 14, 7, 8, 6)		56	2.09	0.96	1.00	5.00

Based on Table 3, the English secondary students learning at one of the well-known private schools in Poipet Town, Bântéay Méanchey Province, Cambodia, valued item 5 the highest (item 5, $M = 4.52$, $D = 0.66$). Most secondary students in that region, closer to Thailand, believed that English was the most crucial subject. They encouraged every student to learn English as a foreign language. Then, for future schools after graduating grade 12, those secondary-level English students thought that English was a fruitful means to boost the educational quality at the future university (item 12, $M = 4.46$, $D = 0.66$). Secondary English learners were positively motivated to learn and enjoy English by living in a technologically advanced world where most people used English widely and meaningfully. (item 11, $M = 4.39$, $D = 0.65$). Then, they indicated the benefits of learning English, which could lead to bright future careers (item 10, $M = 4.30$, $D = 0.69$).

As reported in the above paragraph, secondary-level students positively valued English as the primary means to help them when pursuing education at universities. Then, this aim could lead to their ambition of studying abroad, where people worldwide deliver knowledge through research and cooperation in English (item 13, $M = 4.27$, $D = 0.70$). Next, Table 3 further explains that the students showed excitement any time it was the English class. Excitement was the critical concept of positive attitudes toward learning English (item 1, $M = 4.13$, $D = 0.51$). Table 3 additionally reported that English was the secondary-level students' favorite subject (item 3, $M = 4.02$, $D = 0.80$) and their great helper in mastering various subjects at higher levels of education (item 9, $M = 4.02$, $D = 0.94$). That is why they did not hesitate when they had the opportunity to practice English (item 2, $M = 3.79$, $D = 0.62$).

Studying English with a teacher ensures accurate errors, motivation, and customization to meet the needs of each student. Moreover, it offers structured, instantaneous feedback, motivation, interactive activities, cultural understanding, and personalized learning. Therefore, students should have been taught correctly; otherwise, they felt hostile and complicated when learning English. Similarly, Table 4 proved that students at the secondary level sometimes thought that English was the most difficult language to learn (item 4, $M = 2.77$, $D = 1.01$). This pointed out that they felt more confident with learning it. In Cambodia, any student who could master English would benefit from the National Exams. Moderately Cambodian secondary-level English students want to learn English to pass the exams (item 14, $M = 2.3$, $D = 1.03$). As reported in the above paragraph, secondary-level students positively valued English as the primary means to help them when pursuing education at universities. Then, this aim could lead to their ambition of studying abroad, where people worldwide deliver knowledge through research and cooperation in English (item 13, $M = 4.27$, $D = 0.70$). Next, Table 3 further explains that the students showed excitement any time it was the English class. Excitement was the critical concept of positive attitudes toward learning English (item 1, $M = 4.13$, $D = 0.51$). Table 3 additionally reported that English was the secondary-level students' favorite subject (item 3, $M = 4.02$, $D = 0.80$) and their great helper in mastering various subjects at higher levels of education (item 9, $M = 4.02$, $D = 0.94$). That is why they did not hesitate when they had the opportunity to practice English (item 2, $M = 3.79$, $D = 0.62$).

Table 4. Result of different attitudes of Secondary students toward learning English between male and female. Total of 9 items (5, 12, 11, 10, 13, 1, 3, 9, 2)

Gender	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Male	31	4.24	0.37	.06627
Female	25	4.17	0.43	.08562
Total in average	56	4.21	0.40	0.07594

Table 5. Levene's Test for Equality of Variances

Difference between male and female secondary-level students' attitudes toward learning English (Reasons) through a total of 9 items (5, 12, 11, 10, 13, 1, 3, 9, 2)

Levene's Test for Equality of Variances					95% Confidence Interval of the Difference		
F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Std. Error Difference	Lower	Upper
.30	.58	.70	54	.485	.07	-.13876	.28844

.69 47.68 .493 .07 -.14289 .29256

When comparing the Mean difference between males and females of the secondary-level English students, Table 4 shows that with (M=4.24, D= 0.37), the male students valued the root cause, encouraging them to learn English more highly. There was (M=.0748) difference between the genders of male and female of all the students in which the Mean showing reasons to learn English of the female students was (M=4.17, D= 0.43). However, there was no difference between their attitudes regarding reasons to learn English because the compared mean T shows the p value=.58, which is over .05. The author concluded that there was no difference between male and female students' attitudes showing reasons for learning English. In general, all of them had very positive attitudes toward learning English and widely accepted the reasons as shown in items nine items (5, 12, 11, 10, 13, 1, 3, 9, 2), (M= 4.21, D= 0.40).

Table 6. Result of different attitudes of Primary students toward learning English between males and females. Total of 5 Items (4, 14,7, 8, 6)

Gender	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Male	31	2.11	0.83	0.1492
Female	25	2.06	0.52	0.1036
Total in average	56	2.08	0.67	0.1264

Table 7. Levene's Test for Equality of Variances
Difference between male and female secondary-level students' attitudes toward learning English through a total of 5 Items (4, 14,7, 8, 6)

Levene's Test for Equality of Variances						95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Std. Error Difference	Lower	Upper
2.68	.11	0.28	54	0.78	0.05	-0.32845	0.43581
		0.30	51.07	0.77	0.05	-0.31102	0.41837

This part shows how secondary-level English students value English in General. The authors wanted to know whether they had more positive or negative attitudes. That is why item 4 explored whether they thought English was the most difficult language to learn. Item 14 dug out whether they just wanted to pass the English exams. Item 7 proved their confidence, whether they were embarrassed when learning or speaking English. Next, item 8 wanted to know whether the students considered learning English unimportant. Finally, item 6 checked whether those students liked or disliked English. From the report in Table 6, the female students were more optimistic about learning English (M= 2.06, D= 0.52) and the male students (M= 2.11, D= 0.83). The lower the Mean value was, the more positive it was because of how negative they were toward learning English. All 56 students moderately valued the negative attitudes (M= 2.08, D= 0.67). This shows that they were so confident. Then, when the authors checked whether there was any difference between males and females related to the attitudes showing confidence in learning English, Table 7 shows no difference. With F value (F=2.68, P=.11), the p-value is higher than .05, which indicates no difference between males and females related to the students' attitudes showing confidence in learning the English language.

Table 8. Result of different attitudes of secondary students toward learning English between males and females through the total of 14 Items

Table 8. Levene's Test for Equality of Variances of difference between male and female of the primary students' attitudes

Levene's Test for Equality of Variances				95% Confidence Interval of the Difference			
F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Std. Error Difference	Lower	Upper
2.845	.097	.679	54	.500	.06728	-.13150	.26606
		.712	51.000	.480	.06728	-.12238	.25695

Table 8 indicates whether there was no difference between males and females in the whole study. It proves the F value ($F=2.845$) and P value ($P=.097$). Since the P value is higher than 0.05, the study can conclude that there is no difference between males and females related to the attitudes toward learning English among secondary-level English students in the well-known school in Poipet Town, Banteaymeanchey Province, Cambodia.

The study aligns with the research task conducted by Soleimani and Hanafi in 2013. The study pointed out that male students tend to have more positive views than female students. Despite some fear and problems, Pizzaro's 2017 research on engineering students at the University of the Balearic Islands discovered a positive attitude toward English and an integrated desire for learning. The result conforms to the study by Kifayatullah et al. (2023). His study highlighted no statistically significant difference in students' attitudes by gender. More remarkably, their study further revealed that the female students displayed slightly more positive attitudes towards English than their male counterparts. Based on Kara (2009), students with positive attitudes develop effective study techniques and problem-solving abilities, which are advantageous for academic and personal growth.

Similarly, Pizzaro (2017) reported in his research that the general sentiments of students toward the English language were predominantly favorable. The research findings also pointed out that engineering students were inclined towards acquiring English language skills with an integrative motivation. Nevertheless, the students exhibited significant second language (L2) anxiety. The research revealed that students' general attitudes towards the English language were predominantly positive. Additionally, the study revealed that engineering students demonstrated an intrinsic solid motivation towards acquiring proficiency in the English language. Notwithstanding this, the students exhibited a notable degree of second language (L2) anxiety.

CONCLUSION

The trend of studying English as a second language is rising in the modern era. Younger children learn English, which is required in many national curricula. Still, what particular advantages come with learning English? Whatever their career goals—traveling the world or getting a new job—learning English can help students advance in their personal and professional lives. They can network with people worldwide, compete in the global job market, and grow their professional network. This study investigates the attitudes of secondary English students in Banteay Meanchey, Cambodia, characterized by a predominantly migrant-based population. The research aims to emphasize the substantial influence of migration choices on these individuals. The findings in the study conducted in Poipet Town, Banteaymeanchey Province, Cambodia, revealed no statistically significant disparity in the attitudes towards learning English among secondary-level students based on gender. The obtained P value, which exceeded 0.05, indicates that the observed difference is not statistically significant. However, students still showed moderate confidence that relevant educational stakeholders should find modern methodological methods of teaching and learning English to motivate or help them learn better on time.

RECOMMENDATION

Educators should strive to create a supportive and inclusive atmosphere in the educational context, promoting a passionate commitment to acquiring the English language by incorporating engaging games, musical compositions, and enjoyable activities. The utilization of genuine materials, such as news articles or films, has the potential to significantly augment students' motivation and involvement in acquiring English language skills. In order to foster favorable dispositions towards the acquisition of English language skills, educators must furnish

students with constructive feedback of substantial value. Educators possess the capacity to bolster students' self-confidence and drive to develop their English language skills by discerning their strengths and areas in need of improvement.

Within the framework of a prestigious private educational institution in Cambodia, there exists a prevailing aspiration among the student population to engage a substantial cohort of international educators. Moreover, implementing innovative educational programs is paramount in the 21st century. It is crucial to prioritize the development of a thorough comprehension among these students, providing them with abundant opportunities to actively engage in the educational material presented within the classroom environment. Schools should incorporate supplemental learning activities that promote critical thinking to ensure that students remain engaged with the educational material teachers present.

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